

Truncated R code for–CIIE 2018 folio number 2018062802133: A Computational Literature Review of Educational Innovation

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Introduction

In this short document I provide the R code to summon the data and work with it in R. I include several .rda files, and show background information. The first objective is to load the 'bibliometrix' package and work from it (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). Several datasets have been uploaded to the data repository accompanying this document (M. A. Martinez, 2018).

Nota Bene: This documentation was written in December 2018, and functions may become deprecated or augmented at any time past this date.

Reading in the data

Before executing the `load()` command, it is important that you download the .rda files, and include the downloaded files in the proper file path so that R will recognize the file and read it. First, load the biliometrix library, and then load the 'decade_scopus.rda' file.

Load the data. Then use the `ls()` function to find the name of the data. Then explore. The 'decade_scopus.rda' dataset is from the `bibliometrix::convert2df()` function. The function is costly in terms of time and memory, so I have simplified it for you. The name associated with the the .rda file is 'data' (M. Martinez, 2018a).

```
library(bibliometrix)
load("~/decade_scopus.rda")
```

Create the Network Matrix

Next it is time to render a network matrix by the `bibliometrix::biblioAnalysis()` function. This has already been done for you, and the results have been stored in the 'results.rda' file. Use the `ls()` function to find the name of the data. Then explore. Reading the graphs can be tricky, but there are resources out there to help ("Bibliographic coupling," 2018).

```
load("~/results.rda")
```

Explore various functions

From here, you can use the various functions within the Bibliometrix package to explore the data (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2018). It is advised that you limit graphings to only a small

number of edges, or else it will take much time to render the graphs. Additionally, you can use other R packages to get different views of the data.

Work with the Corpus

In order to get the latent meanings behind the subfields in the scopus articles, we can start with coercing the information into a dataframe (Benoit et al., 2018).

Classify the data with Support Vector Machines

The support vector machine approach is taken with the use of the 'RTextTools' package (Jurka, Collingwood, Boydston, Grossman, & van Atteveldt, 2014). Summary performance statistics can be found online (M. Martinez, 2018b).

```
load('~/.Scopus peer review articles/Data Products/rtexttools.rda')
```

References

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